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A Feasibility Study for A Short Duration Human Mission to the Martian Surface

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Abstract. A feasibility study is carried out for Mission MILESTONE, which is a short duration mission with the aim of establishing a long permanence outpost for subsequent exploration. This paper presents the results of this study, both the overall system architecture and the results of detailed investigations into certain aspects of the mission. The Mission MILESTONE (Mars Initial Landing Expedition Towards a New Era) feasibility study focuses on the mission stages from Low Mars Orbit onwards only, and does not carry out a detailed investigation into the Earth-Mars transit. An 180 day transit is assumed each way, with the intention of residing on the surface for 60 days. As the mission is intended as a pre-cursor to exploration missions, it is focused on the establishment of a habitable environment to ensure the supply of sufficient resources required to sustain human life. During this first manned mission to the Martian surface there will also be technology demonstrations, increasing technology readiness levels for the benefit of future missions. This paper first of all

sets out the mission architecture and objectives. It then details the results of the major investigations carried out into key components of the mission and outpost. Finally, the main conclusions of the feasibility study are drawn.

1 Introduction

The next frontier of human space exploration is the exploration of Mars, and the SEEDS (Space Exploration and Development Systems) course project for 2015 considers an initial human landing on the Martian surface. SEEDS VII is an international, multidisciplinary group comprised of students from both the Politecnico di Torino and the University of Leicester. The project takes place over three stages: in Turin working in collaboration with ALTEC and Thales Alenia Space; in Toulouse with assistance from ISAE; and in Leicester within the University of Leicester Space Research Centre.

The SEEDS VII project covers the second step of "Conquest by Humans of Mars in Five Steps". The

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FIGURE 1. Mission MILESTONE Insignia

summary of the findings and the proposed mission to accomplish this task is MILESTONE: Mars Initial Landing ExpeditionS TOWard a New Era. The overall aim for the mission was given as "The initial descent, permanence and departure of humans on/from Planet Mars". Mission MILESTONE will be an early stage mission, which will create an outpost on Mars for further human exploration by subsequent missions. This was determined to be the most cost-effective method, as a substantial outpost would be required to sustain human life on Mars, thus a multi-mission outpost is designed to allow sufficient time for experimenting to build a future permanent outpost. Mission MILESTONE's insignia can be seen in Figure 1, and depicts the Monolith from Arthur C. Clarke's novel "2001: A Space Odyssey" approaching the Martian surface. The use of the Monolith pays tribute not only to the media that inspires space exploration but also the work of previous Mars missions. Beneath the insignia is the motto of the mission: "The first human expedition to the Martian surface".

2 Mission Summary

The mission statement for Mission MILESTONE is "To descend humans to the Martian surface; to ensure their survival through the establishment of a long permanence outpost; to conduct in-situ scientific operations and exploration; and to allow for their ascent from

the Martian surface".

This statement encapsulates the key mission objectives, and the objective of "conducting in-situ scientific operations" will be expanded into a number of scientific objectives in Section 3.

Mission MILESTONE will take place after Mission Orpheus [3], which was designed by SEEDS VI and is intended to take place in 2036. The mission will build on the scientific and engineering knowledge obtained during Mission Orpheus, including the use of the Crew Interplanetary Vehicle (CIV) as a crew transfer vehicle. As Mission MILESTONE is expanding on Mission Orpheus, the interplanetary transfer will not be considered, and the mission is considered to begin and end in Low Mars Orbit (LMO). Mission MILESTONE will take the form of a split mission, with the cargo modules being launched in two windows in 2039 and 2041, and the crew being launched in 2042. These dates were selected using research presented in *Casalino et al.* [12]. The cargo modules will be collected at the outpost location autonomously prior to the crew launch. In order to ensure mission feasibility, the cargo launches will be constrained to using either a Super Heavy Class launcher (e.g. an SLS-2B [27]) or a Heavy Class launcher (e.g. a Falcon Heavy [37]). There will be a total of 15 launches, with 8 Heavy and 7 Super Heavy launches.

The crew of MILESTONE will undertake a 60 day stay in the Martian environment, which includes the transits to and from Low Mars Orbit. The main objectives of the crew phase of Mission MILESTONE are to assemble the outpost and to conduct scientific activities and exploration, including demonstrating in-situ resource utilisation and food production.

A large outpost has been designed, as a key objective of Mission MILESTONE is to provide a habitable environment sized for a long-duration future mission. The overall configuration can be seen in Figure 2, and the modules shown are: two habitable modules, which provide the main living quarters; two greenhouses for food production; a laboratory for conducting in-situ science; two EVA modules to allow access to the Martian surface; and a node to connect these modules. In addition, the Mars Descent Vehicle will allow the crew to reach the Martian surface, and the Mars Ascent Vehicle will transport them back to the Crew Interplanetary Vehicle (CIV) in Low Mars Orbit. The power plants will power the outpost using nuclear and solar power, and the In-Situ Resource Utilisation will help reduce the dependence on Earth in future missions. Finally, the rovers will give both the modules and the crew mobility.

FIGURE 2. Overall outpost architecture

Mission MILESTONE will land in Amazonis Planitia, in a region centred on 15N, 155W and at an elevation of -3.5 km MOLA [29]. The region is thought to be a Noachian impact basin, with Hesperian lava flow and most recently an Amazonian surface [16], with around 6% water content [39]. The region is of geological interest, and also has a volcanic history which may have caused fossils or extant life to be pushed nearer the surface [16].

The mission will deploy four static landers in addition to the modules being discussed, which will be discussed in Section 3. These will be located at Isidis Planitia (12N, 87E), Chryse Planitia (27N, 40W), Elysium Planitia (3N, 155E) and Candor Chasma (7S, 71W). Each of these landing sites were selected in line with the scientific objectives for Mission MILESTONE, and are locations that could be appropriate as future human landing sites.

3 Scientific Objectives and Operations

The crucial justification for a human mission to the Martian surface is the expected increased scientific return. Having humans on Mars will provide a unique oppor-

tunity to understand the biological effects of the Martian environment on humans, which is essential for future manned missions and even possible colonisation. Another advantage, is to the ability of humans that are performing in-situ sample gathering can discern interesting or unusual features among a large variety of samples, which is difficult to achieve remotely. In addition, a greater variety of scientific experiments can be performed with ever more complexity, and higher risk instruments being able to be taken due to the ability of humans to perform in-situ repairs.

3.1 Scientific Objectives

The science objectives for Mission MILESTONE are as follows:

1. *To study the physiological and psychological impact of a Mars surface mission*
2. *To perform in-situ investigations into the Martian environment to support future exploration*
3. *To collect data to support the identification of landing sites for future human missions*
4. *To study the origins and evolution of Mars*

FIGURE 3. Map of MILESTONE landing sites. Image adapted from MOLA topographic map [30]

To achieve these scientific objectives, a scientific architecture comprising of a laboratory module, four static landers, scientific payloads for the rover, human deployable assets and entry probes for each modules (Section 3.2).

3.2 Scientific Payloads

Laboratory Module: In accordance with the outpost layout, the laboratory module will be the same dimensions as the other modules and consists of a rigid and inflatable sections. The rigid section of the module has two bulkheads which forms the decontamination room; dividing non-hazardous experiments and experiments or samples that have been exposed to the Martian environment. The laboratory module has a dedicated sample delivery and return, in order to decrease the risk of forward and backward contamination.

Static Landers: Prior to the descent of the crew onto the Martian surface, the Crew Interplanetary Vehicle will deploy four identical static landers to the locations mentioned previously.

The landed mass of each of the static landers are 162.7 kg with a science payload of 34.2 kg and a maximum power of 142.8 W. The landers will transmit scientific data to the Outpost Control Centre via a 4G-LTE (see Section 11) The scientific payload consists of the following (with the reference instrument cited): 5 metre

depth mole [7]; gamma ray neutron spectrometer [24]; mole head gamma ray spectrometer [35, 2]; sub-surface seismometer [6]; environmental monitoring suite [17]; laser induced breakdown spectrometer [41]; rock abrasion tool [18]; alpha particle x-ray spectrometer [23]; Raman laser spectrometer [32]; magnetometer [21]; robotic arm [5]; panoramic camera [13] and a radiation assessment detector [19]. One of the unique features of the static landers is the mole capable of reaching depths of 5 metres, with a mole head gamma ray spectrometer based on an instrument proposed in *Skidmore et al., 2009* [35].

Rover Scientific Payload: In order to meet the scientific objectives of Mission MILESTONE and reduce the mass and power required, three different scientific payloads have been specified for the rover; a permanent payload, a planetary science payload and an environmental measurements payload. The permanent payload for the rover contains instruments that will provide scientific data for the duration of the rover lifetime, and includes a number of sensors primarily for aimed at radiation and magnetic monitoring. The permanent payload has a mass of 4 kg and requires a power of 13.5 W.

The planetary science payload contains many instruments included on the static landers, as mentioned previously. However, instead of having a mole, the rover planetary science payload will have a core drill capable

of drilling to depths of approximately 5 m. Although having such a large core drill is a risk, humans can carry out repairs, and it was required due to the reduced operation time compared to the mole [34]. The total mass of the payload is 120 kg and has a power of 1.3kW.

The environmental measurements payload on the rover will consist of pressure, temperature and humidity sensors, together with a sonic anemometer for measuring wind speed. The payload has a total mass of 1.6 kg and a power requirement of 5.5 W.

Human Deployable Assets: Human deployable assets (HDAs) will be deployed by the crew of Mission MILESTONE and will be located in the area around the outpost location. The human deployable assets consist of mini-greenhouses, and radiation and environmental monitoring HDAs.

The mini-greenhouses can be used to monitor the growth of plants whilst exposed to various aspects of the Martian environment; for example using Martian soil. The mini-greenhouse has a total mass of 58 kg.

The atmosphere and radiation monitoring HDAs will consist of atmospheric sensors based on the LIDAR instrument used on the Phoenix lander [10], and a variety of radiation monitoring instruments.

Entry Probes: The entry, descent and landing system (discussed in Section 4) is largely dependent on the Martian atmospheric density, and therefore it is necessary to monitor this accurately. To achieve this, entry probes are used. The probe will use the same trajectory as the cargo modules and will be equipped with an accelerometer to calculate the acceleration over the descent. It will send the recorded data to the communications satellite via Ka-band.

Scientific Timeline: Due to the large number of experiments expected to be performed during Mission MILESTONE, and to estimate the science return of the mission, a science timeline was produced. The scientific activities stage of the mission will last approximately 40 days. With four to six EVAs with the rover and two crewmembers possible in this time, the total number of samples that can be fully analysed is 81. After these samples have been fully analysed, the more scientifically interesting will be selected for sample return to Earth.

4 Entry, Descent and Landing

For Mission MILESTONE, a unique entry, descent and landing (EDL) system has been established, due to the large mass of the modules landed on the surface. The

unique features of this EDL system is the use of a 23 m diameter, *Hypersonic Inflatable Aerodynamic Decelerator (HIAD)*, and the modules having wheels and shock absorbers.

First of all it is assumed that a module with a thermal protection system (TPS) is in a stable, 200km altitude Mars orbit. After a Hohmann transfer has been performed, to take the module's orbit to an altitude of 100 km. the HIAD is inflated. The HIAD will cause an aerobraking manoeuvre in the Martian atmosphere, down to an altitude of -2 km MOLA. After this, the TPS and the HIAD will be ejected; and the main thruster will be activated, causing a constant flight path angle descent to an altitude of -2.8 km MOLA. At this level, the main thruster is ejected and the secondary thrusters are activated, causing a vertical descent down to 15m above the landing site, where the module will hover. At this stage, the secondary thrusters are then employed to achieve a horizontal speed to avoid the 15m diameter hole caused by the retro rockets, with the wheeled landing devices activated.

The altitudes of each stage of the entry, descent and landing were optimised using computer simulations, with the diameter of the HIAD also optimised. The results of these simulations, and the establishment of the EDL system described, were then constraints on other aspects of the mission, such as the altitude of the landing site. The maximum altitude of the landing site due to the constraints of the EDL system, is -3 km MOLA. In addition, the simulations provided the estimate for the 10 km x 3 km landing ellipse of each module. For the mass of each module, the mass of the EDL system can be calculated easily, as it was found that the mass of the module and mass of the EDL system had a linear relationship. For example, for the habitable module which has a mass of 29.5 tonnes, the EDL system has a mass of approximately 10 tonnes.

5 Power

Each module will have an Automated Electrical Power System (AEPS) to maintain the modules temperature and communication links between the cargo period and the crew arrival. The AEPS supplies power using hybrid thermal-electric solar panels [28] located on each module.

During the manned period of the outpost power to the habitable modules, greenhouse modules, laboratory, node, EVA modules and ISRU plant will be provided

FIGURE 4. *The dimensions of the module*

by a centralised power source. The Mars Ascent Vehicle and Mars Descent Vehicle will provide their own power as a contingency measure with the MDV operating as contingency shelter and the MAV as an escape vehicle should the main outpost fail. The rovers will have their own power source for nominal use but may be recharged from the centralised power source should the need arise.

The central power system consists of a set of 19, 300 m² self-deploying solar arrays utilising regenerative fuel cells, an 85 kWe Brayton conversion fission reactor and a distribution system. The solar cells have been sized so that independently they can provide power at any point over the Martian year for single habitable module's life support and a connected EVA module (11kWe). The cells are static, southward facing and have a tilt angle of 35°.

The nuclear reactor is a modular heat pipe reactor design [8]. Both heat transfer and heat rejection are performed with heat pipes. The heat pipes are a sealed system with low maintenance, modularity and inherent redundancy. To reduce the harmful radiation dosage that the crew may receive as a result of the reactors fission products the reactor will be positioned 100 m from the outpost and employ a shadow shield. The shadow shield is a layered tungsten, to shield from gamma rays, and lithium hydride to shield from neutron leakage [9]. In the area covered by the shield, radiation can be reduced to near Martian background levels.

The combination of solar and nuclear presents a diverse and robust system. A totally solar solution would be too massive for an SLS-2B and a single nuclear reactor requires days for the fission products to stop emitting

after being turned off, leaving the choice of being exposed to high radiation or foregoing power for days. The proposed configuration will cover the outpost in nominal conditions and supply a meaningful power production from each system independently whilst conforming to the launcher constraints.

6 Module Design

The primary structure of the modules for Mission MILESTONE incorporates both rigid (blue) and inflatable (yellow) sections to utilise a greater volume with a limited launch mass. The inflatable section of the primary structure can be packed up in the longitudinal direction to 60% of its inflated size. Whilst the module is in the launcher fairing, the inflatable part is totally packed and all the subsystems for the module are mounted in the rigid part. Once the modules are landed on the Martian surface and fully inflated, the subsystems are redistributed along the entire length of the module. In the inflatable part, the secondary structures (floor and ceiling) are mounted by the crew in order to utilise the entire living volume. It is expected that the assembly of all modules and the connection to the power supply would take 12 days. An identical structure is used for all the modules in Mission MILESTONE, excluding the Node.

The overall length of the modules, whilst the inflatable section is packed, is restricted by the fairing size of the SLS-2B [27]. As a result the modules have a packed length of 13m and a diameter of 4.5m. The module length when it is fully inflated is 15.7m. The total living volume is 147 m³, when the module is fully inflated and the secondary structure has been assembled. The dimensions of the module are shown in Figure 4.

The primary structure for the rigid section of the modules comprise of the shell, rings and longerons; whilst the inflatable section comprises of the inflatable shell, rings, and extendable longerons when inflated. The rigid shell of the module is made from aluminium with a Kapton layer for insulation, the rings and longerons are made from aluminium-6061. The inflatable shell is made from layers of BetaCloth, Kapton, Kevlar, Polyamide and Nomex. The module also has end caps that are used to close the module volume and provide the ability for standard connection interfaces. The detailed structure of the module is shown in Figure 5. The total mass of the primary structure is approximately 11.5 tons and the total mass of the secondary

FIGURE 5. Primary structure elements of the modules

structure is approximately 1.2 tons.

7 Radiation Protection

A radiation protection system for the primary habitable module used in Mission MILESTONE has been established. The majority of the radiation exposure will be during the cruise phase from Earth to Mars, with no atmosphere providing protection from galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) and solar particles (SPs). The atmosphere of Mars is thin compared to that of Earth and provides only the equivalent shielding from 16 cm of water [22].

A forward Monte Carlo simulation of the radiation environment on the Martian surface was modelled using SPENVIS MEREM models on the Geant4 platform [1, 15, 33]. The sensitive elements of the simulation were modelled as ‘humans’ made of water located in a geometric model of the habitable module as it was designed at the time. The radiation protection employed was using a layer of water within the shell of the module and this thickness was varied during to simulate the effect that this water layer had. The relative effect of this water layer was analysed to accommodate for changes in the module design and is shown in Figure 6.

The water thickness of 10.41 cm, was determined by being supplied by any excess water from buffers for the habitable modules and the greenhouses. As can be seen in Figure 6 this thickness of water used for radiation protection would reduce the relative dose to 69.31% of the dose without any protection besides the module structural components. The 30% reduction in the dose received by crew members on Mission MILESTONE is considered acceptable. However the dose received dur-

ing the surface stay phase of a Mars mission is minimal compared to the transit phase, thus research should be focused on reducing the radiation dose received during transit [20].

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FIGURE 6. The effect of the water shielding layer to reduce radiation dose

8 Habitable Module

The habitable module will be the living quarters for the crew of Mission MILESTONE. There will be two habitable modules at the outpost, each capable of housing six crew members for 60 days. Two have been considered for redundancy, but in a nominal mode of operation, each module will house three crew members. The landed mass of each habitable module is approximately 29.5 tonnes.

The primary habitable module for Mission MILESTONE will also contain the outpost control centre, which is responsible for controlling the operations of the outpost and will be the centralised communications terminal.

8.1 Environmental Support and Life Support Systems (ECLSS)

The ECLSS employed in the habitable module is the baseline design for other systems used throughout all the modules of the outpost, and is thus only discussed here.

The air revitalisation subsystem is responsible for keeping an appropriate amount of oxygen in the modules atmosphere, and removing CO₂. This subsystem consists of an oxygen generation assembly which uses electrolysis, the carbon capture assembly which uses pressure swing adsorption technology and the carbon reduction assembly which consists of a Sabatier reactor.

The atmosphere management, thermal humidity control and atmosphere control and supply subsystem will keep the atmosphere inside the modules at a pressure of 90.5 kPa; reducing the ratio between the outpost atmosphere and the EVA suits to less than 1.2, eliminating the need for pre-breathing for EVAs [26]. In order to aid the fire detection and suppression subsystem, the oxygen can be removed from the atmosphere and the pressure halved during periods of unmanned operations at the outpost.

The fire detection and suppression (FDS) subsystem is essential because flammability range and spread are estimated to have a peak at approximately the Martian gravity environment [38]. The FDS will use portable water-foam fire extinguishers during manned phases of operation, and the generation of an inert atmosphere during unmanned phases. However, the greenhouse cannot be kept inert for long periods and as a result will use an automated system to isolate itself and provide an inert atmosphere if needed.

The water recovery system that the habitable mod-

ule will use is based on the current International Space Station (ISS) water recovery system, which can recover up to 87% of the water content from waste streams [11]. This will need to be supplemented with approximately 1.5 tonnes of water bought from Earth, to provide the 30 kg/day per crew member [43]. Other systems can recover more water content from waste streams but require a larger intake of resources, such as oxygen, and have been deemed unfeasible for a Mars mission.

The waste management subsystem for the habitable modules will use a heat melt compactor, which will produce compressed tiles of waste that can either be incinerated or can be used for additional radiation shielding for the habitable modules. Each habitable module will have its own trash compactor, with greenhouse having its own waste management system, discussed in Section 9.

8.2 Crew Utilities

The crew utilities are the support structures and equipment that the crew will interact with inside the habitable module. The utilities have been divided into subsystems to cover the different functions needed by the crew: food and galley, waste collection services, hygiene, clothing, personal, housekeeping, operational supplies, sleep accommodation and crew health care. The total mass of the utilities is 5.34 tons with 1.80 tons being consumed by 60 day mission and 3.55 tons remaining for future usage.

9 Greenhouse Module

The greenhouse modules have been introduced with the aim of providing a method of food production for future long duration missions. They will only be tested during Mission MILESTONE, but will provide 1.64 kg of fresh food per crew member per day in subsequent missions.

The greenhouse modules share the same primary and secondary structure with the Habitable Module, but additionally have a tertiary structure which consists of a series of four racks, extended along the length of the rigid part and separated with two corridors. The driving factor for the size is the cultivable surface: the configuration assumes the average height available for each plant is 58 cm. This height will guarantee a better visibility and accessibility to each plant, but also a slightly higher distance from the LED during growth.

The greenhouse will use a gravity-assisted nutrient

film technique (NFT) hydroponic growth system. In NFT, plant roots are kept in contact with a few centimetres of water and nutrients which is continually cycled around the system. It is possible to grow most crops with NFT, including potatoes which usually require a solid growth substrate to grow successfully [42]. The benefit of this system is that the steady stream of water and nutrients past the plant roots allows them to absorb as much water as they require, before the water returns to a tank where more nutrients are added as a salt solution.

From Earth-based studies [36], 1 l/min of water flux is required in NFT systems. A water recovery system based on that used in the Habitable Modules will be used, in combination with water recovery from the waste management systems. The greenhouse requires a total of 31.2 kg/day of water to be introduced from external sources (i.e. ISRU), with a further 14.5 kg/day being recovered.

A waste management system was devised which maximises the resources recovered from the modules and minimises the unusable waste produced. The waste from both the greenhouses and the other modules is sterilised, dried and condensed before being incinerated. It is therefore possible to extract CO₂, H₂O from the process, and use excess O₂ produced in the greenhouse to minimise the inputs required.

A dexterous multifunction robot is envisaged in each module to partially automate all the operation needed to be performed in the greenhouse, from the planting of the seeds and moving the plants from germinator trays to growing trays, to helping in checking the growth and the maturation of the fruits.

The crew diet was decided from a number of considerations, one of which was the required dietary inputs stated by NASA [4]. A number of diets were compared, and the diet chosen requires the smallest area of greenhouse by introducing a number of high calorie and fat foods which would be brought from Earth. The total diet provides 2.2 kg of food per astronaut per day, with 560g of this being provided from Earth. The food from Earth includes high calorie foods and dried wheat, rice and beans, as these were deemed too resource-consuming to grown in the greenhouse. The total requirement of food for transport from Earth is 1875 kg, which provides 76% of the calorie content per crew member per day.

In order to ensure sufficient food provisions for a 500 day mission, three contingency considerations were made. These were to double the food being transported

from Earth, to divide the cultivated area over two modules, and to transport the lyophilised equivalent of two months' worth of crops to provide an additional month of food in each greenhouse module. This configuration minimises the volume and mass and provides 30 days of food to allow for failure repair in the worst case scenario of complete failure of production in both greenhouse modules.

10 Rover

In order to provide mobility for both the modules and the crew themselves, two transport rovers are included. These will be capable of both autonomous travel for collection of the cargo modules, and driven operation so that the crew can travel at higher speeds.

However, as Mission MILESTONE is also providing infrastructure for future missions, the Mars Descent Vehicle (MDV) can be combined with the rover to be used as a long-duration, pressurised exploration vehicle. It contains all the necessary life support systems for multiple-day exploration, as the crew will live in the vehicle immediately after reaching the Martian surface.

The rovers have been designed to autonomously collect the cargo modules ahead of the departure of the crew. The power source required has been sized considering the two launch windows for the cargo mission. All the modules have to be in position and working before the crew departure, so this leaves around 640 days for the first window, and only 90 days for the second one. The worst case scenario involves one rover collecting eight modules in 90 days (after the second window), and therefore covering around 280 km, which requires a collection velocity of 0.13 km/h if the rover operates continuously. The power is supplied by 3.7 kW of regenerative fuel cell (RFC) charge power, which are charged from four 1.9m radius solar arrays in a flower configuration. The total mass of solar arrays is 93.5 kg.

Once the crew have landed on Mars, the rover will collect the MDV and transport the crew to the outpost location. An allowance of six hours was used to size this transfer, which results in a speed of 3.6 km/h. This was the limiting case on the power requirements, due to the large mass being transported, and led to a total mass of 7.8 tons for each rover (including all subsystems). Each of the modes of operation, including this and the initial autonomous collection, can be seen in Table 1.

Mode of Operation	Power Source	Working Period	Average Speed	Daily Range
Autonomous Collection (with module attached)	RFC + Solar Arrays - 3.42 kW	24 hours, continuously	0.13 km/h	3.12 km
Autonomous Exploration (without module attached)	RFC + Solar Arrays - 3.42 kW	24 hours, continuously	0.68 km/h	16 km
Autonomous Collection of MDV	RFC - 41.3 kW	7 hours, recharge needed	3.6 km/h	25 km
Autonomous Exploration - Maximum Range (only Rover)	RFC - 16.2 kW	24 hours, recharge needed	3.2 km/h	77 km
Manned Exploration - Maximum Speed (Rover + 2 Astronauts in suit)	RFC - 92 kW	4.2 hours, recharge needed	17.5 km/h	74 km

TABLE I. Modes of operation for the rovers

11 Communications

Two architectures for the communication system have been determined, one for the cargo mission (Figure 7) and another for the crew mission (Figure 8). The architecture is based on an adaptation of Earth cellular networks for the Martian surface, using 4G LTE links between on-surface elements, and using orbital elements to relay communication back to Earth. Both surface and orbital elements of the Earth Ground Station are used, in the form of modified Tracking and Data Relay Satellites (TDRS) for optical communications and the Deep Space Network (DSN) for Ka-band communications.

The architecture for the cargo mission can be seen in Figure 7, and demonstrates the nominal situation (shown as solid lines) and a number of contingency links (shown as dotted lines). The contingency links have been introduced ensure 100% availability of the link except during solar conjunction, and operate at a lower data rate. Only three modules and one transport rover are shown for simplicity; there would actually be 12 modules and two transport rovers.

In the cargo mission, each module is equipped with an omnidirectional 4G LTE band antenna. The transport rovers are equipped with both an omnidirectional antenna and a parabolic antenna (for communication with the communication satellite).

The crew mission architecture can be seen in Figure 8, with four levels of contingency shown as well as the nominal situation. As previously, each contingency link

will operate at a lower data rates, with the exception of the link between the CIV and the Earth Ground Station which will transmit data at the same rate as from the Communication Satellite to the CIV (6.63 Mbps). The three Communication Satellites are also envisaged to transmit data between themselves at this rate.

During the crew mission, contingencies two and four are envisaged to prevent single point failures in the network and cause the crew to be unable to communicate with Earth. The only modules which use parabolic antennae are the exploration vehicle (0.5 m 4G LTE), the Outpost Control Centre (2 m Ka-band) and the CIV (0.35 m optical). All other modules have omnidirectional 4G LTE antennae, and the CIV also has an omnidirectional Ka-band antenna.

The Transport Rover and Exploration Vehicle have been included as separate elements as there are different data requirements in the crew and cargo phases, and to cover the option of using the MDV for exploration (see Section 10). However, the antennae in use are the same.

The Communication Satellites provide a key part of the communication network. They will have four antennae: a 0.35 m diameter optical antenna; a 2 m diameter parabolic Ka-band antenna; and a 3 m diameter parabolic 4G LTE antenna. As the frequency of 4G LTE is only approximately 800 MHz, from an Areostationary orbit the antenna has a footprint of over 10000 km (calculated based on [40]), which will be more than sufficient to cover the range of exploration without reorientation being required. The Communication Satellites will be solar powered, with regenerative

FIGURE 7. Cargo mission communications architecture

FIGURE 8. Crew mission communications architecture

fuel cells being used to provide additional power.

12 In-Situ Resource Utilisation

Mission MILESTONE will bring all resources necessary for the survivability of the crew for the 60 days on the Martian surface. However, due to the intention to

create a long permanence outpost, it is intended to provide in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) for a number of key resources. When the crew of Mission MILESTONE leaves Mars, the ISRU will collect all the resources that are necessary for the next mission, before the next crew depart from Earth. The physical processes used in the ISRU system are shown in Figure 7. The

FIGURE 9. ISRU schematic of the processes for the production of liquid oxygen and methane

Martian soil and atmosphere are processed in order to produce the resources required, using the Sabatier reaction, electrolysis and CO₂ acquisition.

The ISRU system has been sized based on the reference system discussed in Rapp, 2008 [31]. The requirements for the ISRU system have been summarised in Table 3. The requirements for the preparation of the Outpost between Mission MILESTONE and the subsequent long duration mission and the daily resupply needs for the long duration mission have been discussed. The maximum values required per hour were used to size the total system, which are those for the outpost preparation and lead to a total mass of 7.5 tons.

The system requires 60 kW of power during operation, with the largest contribution coming from the water extractor and processor. It is assumed that the system operates 24 hours a day, and that there will be 540 days between the end of Mission MILESTONE and the start of the next mission.

13 Ascent

A Martian Ascent Vehicle will be used to return the crew from the Martian surface to the orbiting Crew

Interplanetary Vehicle. It is sized to return all 6 crew members and a supply of Martian samples. The vehicle has life support for 3 days and uses a dedicated EVA module for crew entry and exit. The EVA module will remain on the surface.

The Mars Ascent Vehicle will use 5 liquid methane/liquid oxygen burning engines comparable in design to the hydrogen burning RL-10 engines. The engines will exert 350 kN of thrust to launch the MAV which is then throttled to 150 kN to pitch the vehicle over so that it has no radial velocity from the surface of Mars. At this point a series of Hohmann transfers are initiated to bring the MAV to rendezvous with the CIV. The MAV will be shipped as part of the cargo mission, fully fueled with the propellant stored in cryocooler tanks.

The MAV will have two available launch windows a sol if the CIV performs station keeping and the MAV first launches to a 200 km parking orbit. The vehicle will autonomously dock with the CIV and the ascent vehicle will be discarded in a graveyard orbit.

The MAV total wet mass is 26 tonnes with 19 tonnes of propellant, calculated from the manoeuvres required, a capsule of 4.6 tonnes, sized from a NASA parametric

Category	Technology	2015	2017	2019	2021	2023	2025	2027	2029	2031	2033	2035	2037	2039	2041	2043	Reference	
Life Support and Asset Protection	Particulate monitoring	TRL 3		TRL 8 in 2018													ESA	
	Chemical-microbial safety (MIDAS)	TRL 4		TRL 8 in 2018													ESA	
Novel Energy Production and Storage	Hydroponic growth mechanisms, specifically nutrient film technique	TRL 2				TRL 5											TRL 8 needed	ESA
	Photovoltaic power production (solar cells)	TRL 3				TRL 8 in 2021											TRL 8 needed	ESA
Advanced Propulsion	Regenerative (High Temperature PEM) fuel cell	TRL 5															TRL 8 in 2025	ESA
	Super-heavy/rocket (SLS class)	TRL 5	TRL 8 in 2017															NASA
Thermal, TPS and ATD Aspects	Long life cryogenic system	TRL 2				TRL 5											TRL 8 needed	ESA
	LOX/CH4 engine	TRL 3		TRL 6													TRL 8 needed	NASA
Advance Structures and Mechanisms	Advanced, smart and reusable TPS technologies	TRL 2															TRL 8 in 2023	ESA
	Lightweight habitat structures with the views: deployable/inflatable	TRL 5															TRL 8 in 2022	ESA
Communication, Remote Sensing and Imaging	Low gravity sampling acquisition and gathering mechanisms	TRL 3	TRL 5														TRL 8 needed	ESA
	Bio-containers mechanisms for planetary sample protection	TRL 3															TRL 8 needed	ESA
Life Support and Asset Protection	Ultra-light and stable deployable structures, view ports, inflatable ascent capsule	TRL 3															TRL 8 in 2022	ESA
	Booms and modular structures, reusable elements	TRL 2															TRL 8 needed	ESA
Communication, Remote Sensing and Imaging	Optical communication links	TRL 3															TRL 8 in 2022	ESA
	Terrestrial network topologies and technologies for planetary surface communications	TRL 6															TRL 8 needed	NASA
Life Support and Asset Protection	Advanced, smart and reusable TPS technologies	TRL 5															TRL 8 in 2020	ESA
	Lightweight habitat structures with the views: deployable/inflatable	TRL 5															TRL 8 in 2020	ESA

FIGURE 10. Mission critical technologies TRL roadmap

Technology	Description / Capability Performance Goal	Current TRL	Final TRL	Maturation Time [Years]	Reference Agency
Water recycling system	Recycling of grey water and urine, with the possibility of also combining the water from the waste management. High efficiency and low maintenance desired.	3	5	5	ESA

TABLE 2. An example of an enhancing technology for Mission MILESTONE

Activity		H ₂ O [kg]	CH ₄ [kg]	CO ₂ [kg]	O ₂ [kg]	N ₂ [kg]
Outpost Preparation	Total Requirement	42766	5361	–	14950	93
	Requirement per Hour	3.3	0.4	–	1.15	0.007
Daily Supply	Re-Requirement per Hour	3.23	0	0.2	–	0.007

TABLE 3. ISRU resource requirements

model [25] and the remainder being the rocket engines and associated structures.

14 Technology Output and Roadmap

For Mission MILESTONE, a number of technologies that are required for the mission, but which are not yet fully developed have been identified. The maturity of a technology is stated by the technology readiness level, and for Mission MILESTONE, the technology readiness level for systems and sub-systems needs to be at least *TRL 8*.

As a result a number of technologies that need to be matured before the launch for Mission MILESTONE have been categorised into *mission enhancing*, *mission enabling* and *mission critical technologies*. However, it has not been determined how the technologies could be matured or whether it would be possible in the time-frame specified; they are simply presented as criteria that must be met for the mission to be possible. The current timeline for maturing technologies was identified using the *ESA Exploration Technologies Roadmaps 2015* [14] and the *2015 NASA Technology Roadmaps* [28]. Example technologies are given here; a complete list is available on request from the authors.

Mission enhancing technologies are classed as such if it would enhance the efficiency of the mission but do not determine the feasibility of Mission MILESTONE. An

example of an enhancing technology is shown in Table 2. The column “Maturation Time” refers to the *Minimum Time to Mature Technology*, and is defined based on information given in the roadmaps.

Mission enabling technologies are classed as such if a future 500 day missions would not be feasible without. Examples of enabling technologies are shown in Table 4.

The mission critical technologies were also identified, and can be seen in Figure 10. Technologies are classed as mission critical if the 60 day surface stay of Mission MILESTONE would not be feasible without them.

As can be seen in Figure 10, there are several technologies that could not be identified in the *ESA Exploration Technologies Roadmaps 2015* but could be found in the *2015 NASA Technology Roadmap*. However, particular attention should be paid to the need for an ascent capsule as shown in Figure 10. The complete unit of an ascent capsule was not found in either the *ESA Exploration Technologies Roadmaps 2015* [14] or the *2015 NASA Technology Roadmap* [28].

15 Conclusions

Mission MILESTONE will be a short duration mission to the surface of Mars, landing a crew of six humans on the Martian surface in order to establish a long-term outpost for future exploration. The mission will take the

Technology	Description / Capability Performance Goal	Current TRL	Final TRL	Maturation Time [Years]	Reference Agency
Advanced shielding structures (radiation, meteoroids, dust)	Pressurized structure designs with integrated micro-meteoroid orbital debris, radiation, and permeability protection, electrical harnessing, thermal control, and sensor subsystems.	3	8	7	ESA

TABLE 4. An example of an enabling technology for Mission MILESTONE

form of a split mission, with the cargo being launched in 2039 and 2041. The cargo mission will deliver 14 modules to the Martian surface and three communication satellites to Areostationary Orbit.

The crew mission will follow in 2042, once the modules have been successfully assembled at Amazonis Planitia, allowing a 60-day period of human surface operations and exploration.

The outpost established is intended to allow future long-duration exploration, with an aim to reducing the dependence on Earth for resources. The presence of a greenhouse and an ISRU plant will provide food, water and oxygen which are crucial to human survival.

The scientific operations taking place in Mission MILESTONE are led by four key science objectives: studying the physiological and psychological impact of a Mars surface mission; performing in-situ investigations into the Martian environment to support future exploration; collecting data to support the identification of resources for future human missions; and studying the origins and evolution of Mars. The science objectives defined the scientific architecture of the mission, in particular introducing a number of static landers to allow for scientific operations over a larger portion of the Martian surface, and a number of probes to better analyse the atmosphere in order to verify the entry, descent and landing process.

In order for Mission MILESTONE to be feasible, a number of technologies identified must be matured, with a particular focus on the mission critical technologies. However, given sufficient investment and resources, Mission MILESTONE could be a robust and important step in human space exploration.

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